

STUDY OF ACADEMIC LIBRARY SECURITY GUIDELINES

Library Science

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Abstract: *This paper has aim to find out guidelines for security of academic libraries. This study has overview the rules and guidelines like General Financial Rules (GFR) -2005, Govt. of India, Bureau of Indian Standards. (1998). IS114489- Code of Practice On Occupational Safety and Health Audit, National Assessment and Accreditation Centre (NAAC) guidelines (SSR), American Library Association (ALA) Guidelines for the Security of Rare Books, Manuscripts, and Other Special Collections, American College and Research Libraries (ACRL) Guidelines Regarding Thefts in Libraries, etc.*

Key words: *Library Security Guidelines*

1. Introduction

Security is an important factor of all organizations to carry day to day function smoothly. The aim of security is to prevent loss from any type of threat. All departments, institutions, organizations and financial issues are responsible for protecting their assets, personnel and physical security. Libraries support educational programme of learning, teaching and research in educational organization.

Library reading material is constantly needed security because of damage of library material by atmospheric hazards, natural threats, user and staff behavior etc. Libraries have incurred huge amount on reading material therefore security is more important issue. Libraries are facing various security related problems like aggravated assaults, simple assaults, robbery, theft, harassment, delinquent activities, pickpockets, crime, which are committed by staff or user. **Maslow's Need Theory-** Present study is considered Abraham Maslow's theory of a pyramid shaped hierarchy. It consist physiological needs, personal safety (security), social affiliation; self-esteem and self-actualization. It reflects in each and every institution need of safety (Security) with establishment, social responsibilities and esteem by quality services and actualization of institution by constant services. It means after the establishment of institution just next issue is security of its asset, user and employee.

2. Objectives of Study are

1. To identify the security guidelines for academic libraries;
2. To study the need of academic library security guidelines;
3. To know the guidelines, rules and regulations for academic library security.

3. Research Methodology

There are several research methods. These are descriptive, future research, historical research etc. The Descriptive method is used for the present study.

4. Review of Literature

American Library Association (ALA) (2006), American College and Research Libraries (ACRL) (2003, 2006), ACRL- RBMS (2012), Khan, the Council for Museums, Archives and Libraries. (2003)., Shuman, A.B. (1997, 1999, 2002) have provided outlines or guidelines for library security.

5. Need of Library Security Guidelines

Present study has aim to find out various guidelines and policies regarding academic library security. The topic has been raised by several library problems like inventories, stock verifications, loss, theft, misplacement etc. The study has tried to identify the problems, find out generated security guidelines and rules and regulations. The study has provided list of security guidelines. Many examples are found in literature regarding loss of libraries due to different reasons and hazards on international, national and local level. Library administrators should identify the collection need of security broadly. Prevention of library material from theft, mutilation, misplacement, loss, missing, fire, flood and vandalism is important. This is the area which has been most widely ignored. Present study has been endeavoring to study the present guidelines and rules and regulations for academic libraries.

It is not possible to know library security aspects without security education and guidelines. Many libraries are missed or lost their rare collection. Every library needs policies, procedures, rules and regulations for dealing with safety and security concerns. Guidelines are providing pathway to implement security in library.

6. Library Security guidelines, rule and regulation for academic libraries

Special security plan or guidelines is not prepared or provided by any organization or agency in India for academic libraries. But some inventory provisions are made in Government regulations for counting and withdrawal of equipments and physical assets not for security. Physical verification of asset is the process to find out loss and damage of collection, equipment and property.

The Government policy and regulation defines security as “the assurance that information, assets and services are protected against compromise and individuals are protected against workplace violence.”

Today’s globally free and highly technological surroundings effect requires guidelines for security of social public organizations. On international platform there are many guidelines and rules framed by their Governments and related organization administration and authorities. These are ALA, ACRL, guidelines, surveys organized by British National Libray, Nagiran Libray, and study of Library of Congress etc.

Present study has find out these security guidelines from available sources; these are GFR-2005- *General Financial Rule 2005*, Government of India resolution for financial matter, Bureau of Indian Standards. (1998). ISI14489- *Code of Practice On Occupational Safety and Health Audit*, National Assessment and Accreditation Centre (NAAC) guidelines (SSR), University rules and regulations, American Library Association (ALA) *Guidelines for the Security of Rare Books, Manuscripts, and Other Special Collections*, American College and Research Libraries (ACRL) *Guidelines Regarding Thefts in Libraries*, etc.

6.1. General Financial Rules 2005 (GFR 2005)

General Financial Rule 2005 (GFR 2005), it has comprised rules and regulation dealing with financial matter for offices of government of India. Means it is mandatory to every individual, organization and institution, which uses Indian money. General Financial Rules were first issued in 1947 and modified in 1963 and 2005. Government of India (2005).

It outcomes that are necessary to achieve a proportionate and risk managed approach to security that enables government business to function effectively, safely and securely. Government departments, institutions, organizations and financial issues are responsible for protecting their assets, personnel and physical security according to these rules and as appropriate to their business needs and circumstance. Departments and Agencies are best placed to assess the risks they face, and must develop their own security policies in line with this framework.

It also covers General Principles relating to expenditure and payment of money, definitions of losses, inventory management, grants-in-aid and loans, budgeting and accounting for externally aided projects, Government guarantees, instructions for regulating the enforcement of responsibility for losses etc. It has also added procedure for the preparation of detailed estimates of receipts, rules regulating to purchase of stationery and assets, accession register, register of fixed assets, stock register of consumables such as stationery, chemicals, spare parts, physical verification of fixed asset, verification of consumables, procedures of verification, stock verification or inventory, rules for loss, disposal, register of assets of historical / artistic value etc.

It has also included Rule 194 for Physical Verifications of Library Books. (i) Complete physical verification of books should be done every year in case of libraries having not more than twenty thousand volumes. For libraries having more than twenty thousand volumes and upto fifty thousand volumes, such verification should be done at least once in three years. Sample physical verification at intervals of not more than three years should be done in case of libraries having more than fifty thousand volumes. In case such a verification reveals unusual or unreasonable shortages, complete verification shall be done. (ii) Loss of five volumes per one thousand volumes of books issued / consulted in a year may be taken as reasonable provided such losses are not attributable to dishonesty or negligence. However, loss of a book of a value exceeding Rs. 1,000/- (Rupees One thousand only) and rare books irrespective of value shall invariably be investigated and appropriate action taken.

Proper Stock Disposal Register. - The Treasurer shall enter all securities returned or sold by him in a register in Form 3. Returns shall also be entered in register, where the amount returned will be deducted from the capital of the endowment concerned. Format of register is given to maintain record. It is compulsory to follow the rules and regulation of GFR in India for all institutions and organizations.

6.2. NAAC

The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC), as an autonomous institution of the University Grants Commission (UGC), has been entrusted with the responsibility of Assessment and Accreditation of Colleges and Universities in India. NAAC has

also carefully pointed out security in his ‘*Best Practices in Library and Information Services’ Guidelines*. It is also covered in extended hour service, web and e-resource service, electronic surveillance system, RFID, EM tags etc for security, Group concessional Night Services offer for outside students and scholars in accessing e-resources. All these practices NAAC has requisite to better security. NAAC(2005). NAAC has framed the questions on security in profile ‘institutional data’ part I. Its main object is to know how institutions maintain security of the institutional assets, students, staff, and users.

NAAC required information of colleges about security. These questions are, how does the library ensure access, use and security of materials? Describe the safety measures provided by the institutions like security and adequate lighting etc., How does the institution ensure safety and security of the students, faculty and the institutional assets?, Give details on available residential facility for the staff and occupancy constant supply of safe drinking water and Security.

NAAC has set security as one of the indicator in his IQAC manual implicated in 2007 under Key aspect of student support assessment indicators with credit of 30 marks, it is (5.206) “Make the campus safe for students with adequate security and lighting.” NAAC (2007)

6.3. American Library Association (ALA)

The American Library Association is published document about library security (Library Security 2001) summarized most of the five factors in the house model. ALA had emphasized the need to protect library buildings, their employees and users, suggesting preventing actions to combat collection loss, formulating disaster plan and security policy, assigning and training staff to handle security issues. All library security related issues like rules, guidelines covered in this guideline published entitled on *Guidelines for the Security of Rare Books, Manuscripts, and Other Special Collections*. ALA, (2001).

6.4. American College and Research Library (ACRL)

The Association of College and Research Libraries (2003, 2006) has also published two guidelines for handling theft in libraries and for handling rare and special collections. Entitled on *Guidelines Regarding Thefts in Libraries*. In this paper we propose to close this gap by introducing an assessment instrument that has been found to be reliable and usable in assessing the collection security management in libraries in a more holistic approach. It also covers all aspects of collection security and prevent collection form theft. ACRL (2003, 2006)

6.5. University Grants Commission (UGC)

University Grants Commission (UGC) has established the committee “Joint Cadre Review Committee (JCRC) on uniform staffing pattern of the non-teaching staff of Central Universities, The report of JCRC suggested 15 cadres have been placed before the Commission, one of them recommendation is given for ‘Security Services’ for universities and colleges. The Commission has decided that JCRC may be asked to review its report in the light of Sixth Pay Recommendations of the Government of India and submit the same in accordance with the provisions of Sixth Central Pay Commission extended to the employees of Universities. It means UGC creates awareness of security and serious about security of educational institution such as various departments and libraries in university. The objective of the JCRC is to recommend

complete framework of the detailed uniform service conditions for the non-teaching staff (Group A, B, C & D) of these institutions. University Grant Commission Annual Report (2009)

The institution shall tighten security in its premises, especially at vulnerable places and intense policing by Anti-Ragging Squad, referred to in these Regulations and volunteers, if any shall be resorted to at such points at odd hours during the first few months of the academic session. UGC (2009)

Fresher's shall be lodged, as far as may be, in a separate hostel block, and where such facilities are not available, the institution shall ensure that access of seniors to accommodation allotted to fresher's is strictly monitored by wardens, security guards and other staff of the institution.

The institution shall review and suitably enhance the powers of Wardens and the security personnel posted in hostels shall be under the direct control of the Warden and their performance shall be assessed by them. This means UGC has also stress on implementation of security in all higher education related institutions such as departments, colleges, universities and also in college libraries.

6.6. Academic institutions rules and regulations

Schools and Universities has also state the rules of security in his statutes to maintain assets and services. University has accepted the rules and regulation generated by Central and State Governments time to time regarding student security such as anti ranging circular, don't stop women's staff after working hours and late night hours in office.

All above rules and regulation can work behalf of security. Above all practices, government rules and laws are protecting government assets and illegal issues but didn't for specially security. Government departments should develop their own security policies to assess the risks; separate security policies reduce the risk.

6.7. Bureau of Indian Standards. (1998) IS 14489

Bureau of Indian Standards has published "Code of Practice on Occupational Safety and Health Audit IS 14489: 1998." This Indian Standard has been given a guideline to audit safety aspects in the industrial and other units of concern. While formulating this standard, utmost care has been taken to cover all the possible elements relating to safety. However, it may be reviewed from time to time for inclusion of newer elements which would be necessary due to the reasons intended.

The audit typically applies to, but is not limited to a safety system or elements thereof, and is applicable to process, products, or to services. Such audits are often called 'safety system audit', 'process safety audit', 'product safely audit', 'service safety audit'.

6.8. Other available guidelines for academic campus security

U.S. Department of Education, Office of Postsecondary Education, (2011). Checklist for Campus Safety and Security Compliance. Campus Law Enforcement, Campus Security Authority, Implementation and disclosure of missing student notification procedures for institutions with on-campus student housing facilities. US department of education recorded 20% majority of the sample expressed marginal levels of fear with regard to being alone on campus during the day and 66% at night that's why the good campus security is needed.

7. Conclusion

Security is important to prevent from damage of knowledge resource and spent amount on it for users benefit. There is need to prepare separate check list or guidelines for academic library security. Libraries are spending lot of amount on collection, building and equipment; therefore, security is an essential to protect resource to long term for research and user. Security prevention is the best policy for avoiding of loss and damage. Complete security is not possible at every field or every organization but efforts are needed to determine crime and reduce its risks for secure their core collection; care must be taken in freedom or open access libraries.

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